

Impact of Inspirational Leadership on Safety Management System at Birla White

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Abstract

The role and influence of visible leadership and its commitment have come into sharp focus in the industries worldwide and it recognizes that Inspirational leadership is a key step towards a continual excellence journey of zero harm with an interdependent approach along with motivation and commitment. The role of leadership is to align all workforce through demonstration of commitment, motivation and guidance. Integration of work safety culture in a company can be done by the approach of management principles; one of them is the approach of the leadership system. Strong, effective, and visible leadership is an important factor in creating a safe & healthy working environment. This study aims to analyse the impact of inspirational leadership in safety management system at Birla White, as well as to know the factors and contributors which create significant changes in the cultural shift in the safety excellence journey. This research was conducted by comparative analysis of third-party audit results, interviews and questionnaire

Keywords: *Inspirational Leadership, Safety, Zero harm.*

Study Period: 2019-2022

1. Introduction

Birla White (A unit of Ultratech Cement Limited) is the white cement, putty and value-added products manufacturing unit, having one integrated unit, one grinding unit and one green

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field project with presence of sales and marketing all over the country. In Birla White, safety is an overarching value for the management and leadership team is committed to achieving safety excellence through commitment safe behaviours and role modelling. Good safety culture is a result of value and respect for safety systems, Compliance to safety standards, rules and procedures and demonstration of safety as non-negotiable while working and in day-to-day daily life. To achieve the safety excellence leadership has taken various initiatives to change the behaviour and mind set of workforce through motivation, coaching –counselling, interactions with contractors their supervisors, behavioural based rounds, training and awareness, gap assessment, audits and Inspections, daily plant rounds, self-maintenance and housekeeping drives being first step.

2. A. Role of Leadership

Leadership is a major factor affecting the safety management. Leadership values tend to form the basis for developing a vision and encouraging the culture the organization wants to achieve. Effective leadership plays an important role in ensuring the success of an organization to deal with high levels of uncertainty, which correspond to the characteristics of manufacturing or project. Therefore, a team will be directed to succeed or fail largely influenced by the quality of manager's leadership skills. Safety leadership is a sub-system of leadership and can be defined as a process of interaction between leaders and followers, where leaders can influence followers to achieve organizational safety in terms of factors related to organizations and individuals. Occupational Safety and Health Administration has recognized leadership strength and designated leadership management as a key element in safety issues. Develop and maintain essential safety leadership to reduce accidents and improve safety among employees and workmen. Safety leadership is far more important than policy, through the actions or decisions of safety leaders a clear message to the organization, which policy is important and what is not.

B. Brief Introduction of the Leader

Name –Mr Alok Nigam

Designation –Joint Executive President, Birla White

Group experience –More than 25 Years

Mr. Nigam is having more than 25 years of experience in the ABG. He worked at different capacities in group at Grasim and UltraTech. He is having detailed experience of working with Du Pont safety standards

3. Initiative's taken

a. Walk Through Rounds

As we are aware that unsafe conditions create risk at the workplace and their systematic identification as well as removal is highly required on regular basis. For the same in line with HO, here in Birla White Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam taken lot of efforts and through regular monitoring and motivation WTIs has been started. To review the quality of WTI rounds, PRATIBIMB sessions has also been organised with corporate safety team for their valuable inputs to further improve quality. WTI coordinators also made for better facilitation in the departments.

b. Contractor Connect Sessions

As most of the jobs being done by the contact workmen, so their awareness skill and competency is highly required for safe job execution. In view of the same Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam meeting with different contractors and their supervisors and motivating them towards safety compliance. He is discussing on CSM and other safety standards with them and further guiding to ensure required compliance while executing any job at site.

c. Housekeeping Drive

To improve and maintain the housekeeping at workplace, daily self -maintenance has been restarted under the leadership of Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam where all the WCM teams are joining hand in hand at their defined areas and doing the regular efforts for housekeeping and self-maintenance. WCM cell is monitoring the performance of all the team members and appreciating their efforts. Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam is also joining this drive at various locations and appreciating the team members. As unique imitative some of the employees as well as contract workmen has been invited to share their experience and contribution which was well appreciated and became a motivational drive for all others to engage as well as motivate themselves.

d. Cross Functional Engagement in Shutdowns

Under the guidance of Plant Head, cross functional teams have been made for the round the clock safety coordination during the shutdowns, which resulted in Injury free major

shutdowns where every time more than six hundred persons were invited for major jobs across the plant.

To achieve the same after medical and height phobia test, all the shutdown workmen were given safety induction where they were made aware about the pod system which is made for better identification and to avoid an intermixing. Colour coding also given to all the workmen for the same. Regular tool box talks provided for refreshing the daily job safety requirements.

e. Strengthening of Sub Committees

Under the Apex organogram, various sub committees and ACT groups are working. All these sub committees are aligned with board level sub committees, in which status of key performance indicators and status of important points being discussed and reviewed.

All these sub committees are presenting their status to Apex committee. In Apex Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam being the chairman reviewing the status of all sub committees and after reviewing status of all subcommittee he advised all concerned chairman to strengthen with suggesting way forward.

f. Communication on Safety Standards

Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam is communicating all employees through message on theme of the month. In his message he is explaining need of the requirements to follow the safety standards and advantages of following the same. Such type of mass communications clearly resulted in the explaining expectations of the management towards safety standards and changed the mind set with thinking process of employees as well as workmen towards safety leadership in this excellence jour

UltraTech Cement Ltd.
Unit: Birla White

Dear Colleagues, Greeting to all

"Life Saving Rules" being theme of May,2022 month, I want to re-emphasise on its importance. In Birla White, Life saving rules are very vital in a running plant operation and project activities. The life-saving rules have been created to **keep our people safe and to ensure safe working culture**. This rule provides framework and guidance for safe operations. These rules if not followed has high potential of serious incidents, even leading to fatality. Therefor all must follow them as per intent. These rules are non negotiable and incase of non compliance progressive consequence management may be applied .

Our Life saving rules are :

Control of work rules : 1. Work with relevant work permit, 2. Ensure isolation and Lockout before work begins, 3. Obtain authorization before overriding safety critical equipment.

Personal Safety Rules : 4. Protect yourself from fall when working at height, 5. Obtain authorization before entering a confined space, 6. Do not walk under a suspended load, 7. Obtain authorization before excavation

Site safety rules : 8. Do not work under the influence of drugs or alcohol.

In Birla White life and wellness of our people and their families are of paramount importance. As an organisation we are committed to achieve safety excellence in all aspect.

Let's take a disciplined risk based approach and always ensure compliance of Life Saving Rules. Through this campaign we need to increase awareness levels, ensure self and team follow all the Safety Rules and COVID Guidelines. Review the Safety Standard and ensure quick implementation of gap J cal upon the entire Birla White team to pledge themselves to 100% observance of Life Saving Rules and set an example for our extended community.

Best Wishes

Alok Nigam
Plant Head
Birla White

g. Team Motivation During Daily Plant Rounds

During his daily plant rounds, Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam is motivating the employees as well as workmen towards importance of housekeeping, self-maintenance and compliance of safety standards. He is guiding the workforce that housekeeping is the mother of safety. During his conversations he is explaining the need for involvement of each employee in the journey towards zero harm and guiding them for their regular small regular efforts is important.

h. Involvement in Safety Promotional Programs

Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam is always eager to participate in the safety awareness and promotional actives and programs and during these programs he is addressing all workforce

towards need of involvement of each and every one in this excellence journey and touching most of the workmen and employees through reminding them their efforts. Such type of the energetic involvement resulted in the motivated workforce and team boosted up towards environment, health, safety and started making positive efforts.

I. Efforts Towards Leakage Arrest and Housekeeping

Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam always motivated the workforce towards maintaining good housekeeping in their respective working areas and he always appreciated the team for their contribution in it. He is guiding the head of the depts. and section heads to always maintain housekeeping in their area of operation. During his plant rounds, he always observed the efforts of workforce towards housekeeping and with involvement appreciating their contribution.

j. On Job Motivation to Workforce on Safety

With aim of highlighting the need of safe job execution, as a team leader Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam is always meeting Workforce whenever they are on the job, taking their feedbacks and guiding them on the compliance of Jobs as per risk assessment and permit to work system requirements

k. Contribution in Road and Driving Safety

As one of important requirement under road and driving safety standards was waiting room for drivers, so Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam taken lead and made drivers waiting room for cement drivers. He always explained the “follow two and never three” golden road safety rules to all which are as follows:

1. Always wear a helmet while driving two-wheeler
2. Always wear seat belt while driving four-wheeler
3. Never exceed speed limit
4. Never drink and drive
5. Never use mobile phone while driving

I. Encouragement and Guidance to Workforce

Under the principle of lead by example, through humanitarian approach Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam guiding the engineers and workforce on adopting the safe job execution, 5S and need of elimination of workplace hazards through regular walk-through rounds and addressing the behavioural issues through the behavioural observation rounds.

m. Always Inspiring the Team as Role Model

It is one of the specialities of successful team leader that he always gives credit to the team members. So, in every management forum, Plant Head Mr Alok Nigam always admiring the efforts of his every team member and it gives the motivation of all the members towards doing the best.

n. Efforts During Challenging Pandemic Period

As a role model and team leader Mr. Nigam ensured continuous running of the business operations through following initiatives and by adopting new ways of working with ensuring COVID appropriate behaviours at work place –

1. Regular workplace sensitisation.
2. Marking of social distancing circles
3. Touch less thermal scanning and attendance
4. Regular announcement at entrance.
5. Formulation of various SOPs
6. Use of mask as compulsion
7. POD system and color-coding during shutdown
8. PSSR.

9. Handwashing and sanitisation facility at entrance and at workplace.

Results

Significant improvement in the thought process of workforce towards safety, environment and sustainability.

1. Motivated workforce with high morale.
2. Image building of white cement in UltraTech.
3. Running of plant during major challenging pandemic period.
4. Completion of challenging shutdowns with compliance and zero injuries.
5. Significant % reduction of observations in third party safety audit.
6. Winning Golden Peacock Safety award, 2020, Apex India and ICC OHS awards.
7. Certificate of appreciation by Chief inspector of factories & boilers, Rajasthan on getting more than 80% marks in factory safety award.